

**ANÁLISIS DEL IMPACTO DE LA EXPOSICIÓN
AL IDIOMA FUERA DEL AULA EN LA ESCRITURA
DE LOS ESTUDIANTES.**

Exploring the impact of language exposure outside
the classroom on students' writing.

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RESUMEN

El impacto de la exposición al idioma en el aprendizaje del idioma es reconocido (Pujadas y Muñoz, 2020; Pattermore y Muñoz, 2020), pero pocos estudios han abordado su influencia en la escritura (Strobl y Baten, 2021). Este estudio examina cómo la exposición al inglés fuera del aula se relaciona con la escritura de los estudiantes. Un total de $n = 40$ participantes ($n = 20$ con un nivel B2; $n = 20$ con un nivel C2) participaron en el estudio. El estudio sigue un enfoque de investigación de métodos mixtos y los datos fueron recopilados, por un lado, mediante un cuestionario adaptado de Lasagabaster y Hugué (2007) y una composición escrita que se analizó utilizando la taxonomía de Jacobs et al. (1981). Por otro lado, también se realizaron entrevistas semiestructuradas. Los resultados muestran que la exposición al inglés fuera de la escuela tiene una conexión positiva con las puntuaciones de escritura. Además, existe una asociación positiva entre la participación de los estudiantes en actividades fuera de la escuela y sus puntuaciones de escritura. Las entrevistas revelan diferencias individuales que influyen en la participación en actividades. El estudio sugiere combinar la exposición al idioma en el aula con la participación fuera de la escuela.

Palabras claves: Escritura en tercer idioma, exposición al idioma, medios de comunicación y aprendizaje de idiomas.

ABSTRACT

The impact of language exposure on language learning is acknowledged (Pujadas & Muñoz, 2020; Pattermore & Muñoz, 2020), but few studies have addressed its influence on writing (Strobl & Baten, 2021). This study examines how English exposure beyond the classroom relates to student writing. A total of $n = 40$ participants ($n = 20$ with B2 level; $n = 20$ with C2 level) participated in the study. The study follows a mixed methods research approach and data were collected, on one hand, by means of a questionnaire adapted from Lasagabaster & Hugué, (2007) and a written composition that was analyzed using Jacobs et al., (1981) taxonomy. On the other hand, semi-structured interviews were conducted with ten of the participants. Findings show that English exposure outside of school has a positive connection with writing scores. Moreover, a positive association exists between students' engagement in out-of-school activities and their writing scores. Besides, interviews reveal individual differences that influence activity engagement, subsequently impacting writing scores. These findings suggest that combining language exposure with out-of-school engagement is beneficial for language learning.

Keywords: Third language writing, language exposure, media and language learning.

INTRODUCCIÓN

Language exposure is claimed to be a requirement for language learning (Krashen, 1982), and previous investigations have shown that the amount of language exposure in the classroom is crucial for language learning (Muñoz, 2011; 2014; Llanes & Muñoz, 2013; Sheela & Ravikuma, 2016; Pattermore & Muñoz, 2020). However, other researchers point out that just in-class language exposure is not enough (Benson, 2003; Olsson & Sylvén, 2015; Sundqvist & Sylvén, 2016). In line with previous research that has focused on the role of language learning, the present study aims to explore the impact of the intensity of language exposure outside the classroom on students' written performance. Before proceeding, it is essential to elucidate the concept of out-of-school factors. The phrase out-of-school refers to any activities associated with learning beyond the confines of the classroom, encompassing organic language acquisition and self-directed learning. From this perspective, in the current investigation, we will consider the variables of media (listening to music, watching TV/ films, and social networks) as out of school activities students may engage with and its input on L3 (English) writing.

By engaging in out of school activities, learners may be exposed to the target language. Nowadays, the impact of language exposure outside the classroom has been widely analyzed in relation to the use of Information Communication and Technology (henceforth: ICT). It is widely accepted that the rapid emergence of ICT in all spheres of life has also found its way into students' daily lives, due to the rapid emergence of online streaming platforms besides, there is no doubt that the factor of Media (watching TV, listening to music, or the use of social networks) has found its way into students' daily life,

which can, in turn, be a critical factor for language learning. In fact, the benefits of watching TV on students' learning outcomes have been reported by several researchers (Lee & Révész, 2020; Pujadas & Muñoz, 2020; Pattermore & Muñoz, 2020). It has been pointed out that by watching TV students acquire positive effects on aspects such as the acquisition of vocabulary (Pavia, Webb, & Faez, 2019; Muñoz & Cadierno, 2021; De Wilde *et al.*, 2021), oral performance (Serrano *et al.*, 2011; Saito & Hanzawa, 2018), grammar (Van Den Poel & Leunis, 1999; Lee & Révész, 2020; Pujadas & Muñoz, 2020; Pattermore & Muñoz, 2020) and general English competence (Koolstra & Beentjes, 1999; Bunting & Lindstrom, 2013). However, as far as we know, no study has dealt with the impact of watching TV on students' writing.

Additionally, the effect of listening to music on students' writing has also been explored, reporting a positive effect on students' written performance (Kuppens, 2010; Luarn, Lin & Chiu, 2015; Hanibal-Jensen, 2017). However, research on the use of social networks and language learning presents inconclusive results. While some studies have reported positive effects, (Luarn *et al.*, 2015; Vikneswaran & Krish 2016; Khan *et al.*, 2014; Ekpe *et al.*, 2021; Wilde *et al.*, 2020), others seem to suggest some negative effects of the use of social media on students' written performance (Malaney, 2004; Alwagait, Shahzad, & Alim, 2015).

For example, Luarn *et al.* (2015) found that social media was one of the most important factors that affected students' academic performance and the use of linking words. The researchers found that Facebook usage contributed to students' ability to participate socially and culturally in their new environment. Along the same line, Vikneswaran and Krish (2016) reported that the use of technology in writing tasks made students write

better in English. Similarly, Khan *et al.* (2014) investigation showed that the use of Social Media is significantly associated with students' grades. Similar results were obtained by Ekpe *et al.* (2021), who conducted a study analyzing the effect of social media on academic performance among Malaysian students. A total of 191 students took part in the study. Researchers used questionnaires and administered them to three public universities in Malaysia. Regarding findings, it was revealed that the use of social media as a source of information for studies had a significant effect on the student's writings. Finally, another study, which is worth mentioning, is the one by Wilde *et al.* (2020). Researchers examined the level of English proficiency children can obtain through out-of-school exposure in informal contexts. Language learning was investigated in 780 Dutch-speaking children, who were tested on their English receptive vocabulary knowledge, listening, speaking, reading and writing skills. Information about learner characteristics and out-of-school English exposure was gathered using questionnaires. The findings revealed language improvements in a significant number of children, yet notable individual variations were noted.

Contrary to these findings, negative learning results from spending a high amount of time on social media have been reported. For instance, Malaney (2004) investigated the use of social networks on students' language learning. A total of 490 university learners took part in the study, and data were collected by means of an English test, a questionnaire, and semi-structured interviews. Results from the study showed that students spend most of their online time using social networks and email, surfing the Web, doing coursework and downloading things. The researchers pointed out that students' grades suffered as a consequence of spending too much time on the media. In the same vein, Alwagait, Shahzad, and Alim

(2015) conducted a study aiming to analyze the use of social media and students' academic grades. A total of 108 participants took part in the study. Data were analyzed by means of a questionnaire and semi-structured interviews. The questionnaire gathered data in relation to the usage of social networks. Results from the study showed that the use of social media had a negative impact on students' grades.

Based on the aforementioned studies, we can assert that there appears to be a positive correlation between language exposure through media, primarily watching television, listening to music, social network usage, and reading, and students' written performance. However, a majority of the research has focused on specific aspects such as vocabulary acquisition (Pavia, *et al.*, 2019; Pujades & Muñoz, 2020; Cadierno *et al.*, 2020; De Wilde *et al.*, 2021), oral proficiency (Serrano *et al.*, 2011), grammar (Van de Poel, 1999; Lee & Révész, 2020; Pujadas & Muñoz, 2020; Pattermore & Muñoz, 2020; Cadierno *et al.*, 2020), and overall English competence (Koolstra & Beentjes, 1999; Bunting & Lindstrom, 2013). Moreover, some studies have not comprehensively encompassed all aspects of media (TV watching, music listening, and social network usage), as the current study aims to do. As far as we know there is just one study (Strobl & Baten, 2021) that has examined students' L2 writing and Media (watching Tv, listening to music and use of social media). Strobl & Baten (2021) explored the writing development of 30 Belgian Students in L2 German. Students' writings were analyzed after one semester abroad. Findings from the study showed a positive correlation between writing gains and language contact, and social networks. In line with Strobl & Baten (2021), the present study will examine the impact of language exposure through media on students' writing, in the multilingual setting of the Valencian Community.

Furthermore, based on our current understanding, the studies mentioned earlier have disregarded L3 students and have not accounted for students' multilingual backgrounds (Cenoz & Valencia, 1994; Sagasta, 2003; Sanz, 2008; Arocena 2017; Orcasitas-Vicandi, 2022). Besides, of the above mentioned studies, as far as we know, none has explored the language learning of adult multilingual learners. Hence, the present study aims to add new insights to previous investigations on the impact of media on L3 (English) writing.

The following research questions guided the study.

Research Question I (RQI): Does English contact through media have an impact on students' written performance?

Research Question II (RQII): Does positive engagement with media have an impact on students' written performance?

METHOD

Participants

The current study takes place in the Valencian Community, a Multilingual Community where Catalan and Spanish coexist, and English is learned as an additional language. The context where the present study was conducted was one of the official language schools in the Valencian Community. These centers are specialized in language learning and teaching, and different languages such as Spanish, Catalan, English, French, German, Italian, Russian, Portuguese, Arabic or Chinese are taught. A total of 40 participants, with a C2 level ($n = 20$) and a B2 level ($n = 20$) of English took part in the study. The age of participants ranged from 16 to 59 years old, and the gender distribution was 67.5% female ($n = 27$) and 32.5% male ($n = 13$). In terms of mother tongue, 55% ($n = 22$) of the participants reported their L1 to be Spanish; 12.5% ($n = 5$) reported being Catalan; 30%

($n = 12$) reported both, Spanish and Catalan; and 3% ($n = 1$) reported other languages (see Figure 1).

FIGURE 1

Participants' L1

As shown in Figure 1, participants have at least three languages in their linguistic repertoire: Catalan, the minority language; Spanish, the dominant language in the surrounding sociolinguistic environment and in society at large; and English as a foreign language. For the study, we will explore students' writing in English, although we will also consider the impact of the two official languages Catalan and Spanish on students' L3 writing.

Data collection procedure

In the present investigation, a mixed-methods research approach has been used. Thus, quantitative and qualitative data collection instruments were employed.

Quantitative instrument

Data were collected by means of a questionnaire based on Lasagabaster and Huguet (2007). Participants were given 15 minutes to complete the questionnaire which was written in Spanish and consisted of two parts (see Appendix 1). In relation to the first part of the questionnaire, it gathered general information regarding (i) age, (ii) sex, (iii) level of English (iv) mother tongue and (v) language spoken at home. The second part, it gathered information about the use of Catalan, Spanish and English in out-

of-school contexts. Participants had to choose the language in which they did nine activities: watching TV, listening to the radio, reading books, searching for information (Google), using social networks, listening to music, and video games. In addition, they had to indicate if they enjoyed being engaged in the aforementioned out-of-school activities.

The focus of the present investigation is on the impact of out-of-school contact with the English language on students' writing. We analyzed the information provided in the questionnaire regarding the exposure to English outside the school, and collected and analyzed students' writings in English. Each student wrote a composition (150–200 words) about the "Advantages and Disadvantages of on-line shopping" (See Appendix 2). We

chose this task taking into account the criteria formulated by Jacobs et al. (1981) in their book "Testing ESL Composition: a practical approach", as the author reported that the composition has to be realistic and the topic to be appropriate.

Qualitative instruments

Concerning the qualitative instruments, data were collected by means of an open question ("How do you feel when you write in English?") to be answered, with a minimum of 20 words, after they finished their composition in English. In addition, semi-structured interviews were held individually. The following five questions (see Table 1), guided the semi-structured interviews and provided additional information to the ones provided in the questionnaire.

TABLE 1

Do you like writing in English?
What language do you like the most, Catalan, Spanish or English?
How do you feel when you write in English?
What language do you feel more comfortable with?
Do you think that learning how to write in English is useful?

Coding and data analysis

In the present investigation, a total of 40 written texts in English were analysed. The essays were typed up exactly as they were written in electronic format (.txt). The written compositions were all scored using the taxonomy created by Jacobs *et al.* (1981). This Taxonomy includes a five-component scale: *content* (how well they understood and developed the topic; 30 points), *organization* (how organized, fluent and cohesive the text is; 20 points), *vocabulary* (how sophisticated, effective and appropriate the vocabulary is; 20 points), *language use* (how well com-

plex constructions and grammar are used; 25 points) and *mechanics* (how effectively punctuation and spelling are used; 5 points). They added up to a total of 100 points.

Furthermore, the compositions were rated by the principal researcher and two secondary school English teachers. Following Cohen's (1960) procedure, raters coded independently students' writing according to the dimensions of Jacob *et al.*'s (1981) taxonomy. Before coding students' writings, raters went through two training sessions in order to become familiar with the rating scale and to provide them with specific instruc-

tions on how the compositions should be assessed. Coding resulted in these agreements: 88% for content, 87% for organization, 91% for vocabulary, 83% for language use and 89% for mechanics.

Regarding the questionnaire, data were entered into the Microsoft Access Database. The first step was to create a profile for each of the participants (age, gender and intensity of exposure to the English language). Furthermore, students' intensity of exposure to English outside school was coded by adding the total number of activities in English that students engage in outside the school. In addition, students were divided into three groups according to their level of positive engagement in out-of-school activities in English: Low engagement (1 to 3 activities in which they participated and enjoyed), Medium engagement (4 to 6 activities in which they participated and enjoyed) and High engagement (7 to 9 activities in which they participated and enjoyed).

After typing all the composition and entering data collected in the questionnaire into Microsoft Access Database, Pearson's coefficient analysis was conducted using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) to explore the relationship between intensity of English exposure, enjoyment in using English during school activities, and writing performance.

Finally, qualitative data obtained from the students' interviews were transcribed by the principal researcher and used for further interpretation of the quantitative results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As previously mentioned, the main goal of this study is to explore the impact of students' exposure to English, outside the classroom, on students' English writing. With reference to RQ1 (Does English contact outside the classroom have an impact on stu-

dents' L3 written performance?) We explored whether there was a relationship between English language contact outside the classroom and written performance. Figure 2 shows the percentages of English language contact outside the classroom.

FIGURE 2

Students Percentages of English language contact outside the classroom.

Based on the data, we can see, the most common activity is watching movies in English, with 80% of the individuals engaging in this activity. Following this, 75% of individuals listen to music in English, while 50% watch television programs in English, 40% keep up with English news, and 30% read English books. Additionally, 69% of individuals search for information in English on Google, while 48% use Facebook in English. Finally, only 25% of individuals play video games in English.

From this descriptive data, it can be concluded that watching movies in English is the most popular out of school activity in English. Music in English and watching television programs in English are also common activities. Individuals are also engaged in reading English books and keeping up with English news. It is also evident that the internet is a crucial tool for individuals seeking information in English, with a high percentage using Google and Facebook in English. Fi-

nally, playing video games in English is not as popular compared to other activities. Overall, these findings indicate that individuals are actively seeking opportunities to practice and improve their English skills outside the classroom. After analysing the descriptive data, it is important to determine whether there is a significant relationship between English language contact outside the classroom and written performance.

Subsequent to the performance of the Shapiro-Wilk test, the data do not show a normal distribution. Therefore, a non-parametric Spearman's correlation analysis was conducted, along with a Bootstrap analysis to estimate the sampling distribution of the Spearman correlation coefficient.

The Spearman correlation coefficient between English language exposure beyond the classroom setting and written performance demonstrated a robust and positive relationship ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.01$). Employing bootstrap resampling techniques yielded dependable estimates of the correlation coefficient, with a Bias of 0.000 and a Standard Error of 0.137. The BCa 95% Confidence Interval for the

correlation coefficient was calculated as [0.345, 0.873], indicating a 95% confidence level that the actual population correlation coefficient falls within this interval. Collectively, these findings highlight a substantial association between writing scores and academic performance, indicating the potential influence of extracurricular factors on writing achievement.

Moving to RQ II we were interested to explore if there was a relationship between participants' level of positive engagement, measured by the number of different activities participants enjoy and engage in outside the school, and their writing scores. As illustrated in table 2 participants were divided into 3 groups: high engagers, participants who reported enjoyment by doing from seven to nine activities in English outside school ($n = 16$, 40% of the general sample); medium engagers, participants who enjoyed doing from four to six activities in English outside school ($n = 13$, 32.5% of the general sample); and low engagers, ($n = 11$, 27.5% of the general sample) participants who reported enjoyment from one to three activities in English outside school (see Table 2).

TABLE 2

Participants' level of positive engagement in out of school activities

Level of positive engagement	Number of activities	Participants	Percentage
High	(7-9)	16	40%
Medium	(4-6)	13	32.5%
Low	(1-3)	11	27.5%
Total	(9)	(n = 40)	100%

As observed in table 3, participants with a high level of engagement performed better in their writing skills with a mean of 85 (SD = 17.35), followed by those with a medium level of engagement, with a mean of 74.6 (SD = 14.97), and the low level of engagement group, with a mean of 59.3 (SD = 16.13)

TABLE 3

Mean scores of the English writings for each group according to the level of engagement

Level of engagement	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
High	16	85	17.35
Medium	13	74.6	14.97
Low	11	59.3	16.13

In addition, a detailed analysis of our data shows that those with a level of high engagement scored higher in each of the dimensions that we considered in the evaluation of English writing; content, organization, voca-

bulary, language use and mechanics. Table 4 provides an overview of the mean scores in each of the five components suggested by Jacob's *et al.* (1981) to evaluate writing according to level of engagement.

TABLE 4

Scores in each of the dimensions according to level of engagement.

Written Dimensions	High		Medium		Low	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Content (30 points)	25.18	5.33	22.9	4.83	19.18	4.89
Organization (20 points)	16.87	4.06	15.07	3.33	12.09	3.26
Vocabulary (20 points)	17.68	3.34	15.31	3.11	11.81	3.28
Language Use (25 points)	21.13	4.48	18.07	4.24	13.55	4.48
Mechanics (5 points)	4.12	1.35	3.38	1.16	2.72	0.90

As shown in Table 4, students with a high level of engagement performed better in the five dimensions of the compositions. In addition, if we compare results in the high and medium group, it seems that there are differences in relation to the dimension of content (25.18 versus 22.9) and language use (21.13 versus 18.07). In contrast, when we compare the written production of medium and low engagement, differences are found in language use (18.07 versus 13.55) and vocabulary (15.31 versus 11.81).

Thus, it seems that the level of engagement in out-of-school activities makes a difference in students' writing. However, individual differences are observed considering students' level of engagement and their written performance (see Figure 3).

FIGURE 3

Students' level of engagement and their written performance

As it can be observed in Figure 3, within the low engagement group S8 and S1 scored higher than the rest of the participants in this group, being S8 the one who got the highest score in the written composition, regardless of the level of engagement in out of school activities in English. To further understand these differences we looked at participants' responses during the semi-structured interviews in which they were asked "Do you do any other out-school activities in English? S1 answered "I don't do it on a daily basis because I don't have time, but I always spend my summers in England" and S8 reported, "I don't usually engage in any English activities outside of class, but I do tend to hang out with my English-speaking friend". Thus, our qualitative findings indicate that S1 and S8 engage in out-of-school activities different from the one included in the questionnaire, which involved English language contact through Media, and these activities seem to have a positive impact on English writing.

In the case of medium engagers, Figure 3 illustrates that S4, S10 and S12 scored higher than the rest of the participants in this group. The explanation for this is similar to what we found in relation to the group of low engagers, that is to say, they engage in other out-of-school activities that were not included in the questionnaire. S4 reported, "We usually go to

America every summer, as my brother lives there", S10 answered "In July, I work at a summer school in England, and then I stay for the whole summer" and S12 reported, "I spent the summer in England with a family there to learn English". In contrast, in spite of having a moderate level of engagement, S3 reported a lack of interest "I don't engage in any other activities. I think that contact with English outside of class is not important, and that's why I don't usually have much contact with English outside the class", and S6 mentioned lack of time "No, I don't have time to do another activity, besides I think that in class is when you learn the language". Thus, one tentative hypothesis is that factors such as lack of interest in learning English may trigger less interest in having language contact outside the classroom, and, as a result, resulted in lower scores in English writing. This is an issue in need for further empirical investigation.

Finally, Figure 3 illustrates that participants within the group of high engagement got the highest scores, but S8 got a score lower than those obtained from the group of medium engagers, and S14 and S16 got a score similar to those obtained by the group of low engagements. In all these cases participants reported a lack of interest in using English and a preference to use their L1(Spanish) or L2 (Catalan) when they engage in activities outside the classroom. This is illustrated in the following responses provided by S8 "I prefer to watch movies in Spanish", S14 "I believe that class is where you learn, and outside of class I prefer to use Catalan language" and S16 answered, " Outside of class, I use English very little. I prefer to use my own language".

On the contrary, we also observed that high engagers (S3 and S15) tend to report a positive opinion towards the two official languages (Catalan and Spanish) and English as an additional language. This is illustrated in

the following responses provided by S3 "I enjoy using all the languages I know, I use catalan at home, Spanish with my cousins and I watch films in English", and S15 "I like English Catalan and Spanish and I use all of them".

Although exploring students' multilingual background is beyond the scope of the present study, future studies might consider multilingualism as a variable. This aspect of learners' multilingualism background is crucial to be explored, as evidenced by other studies indicating that a greater number of languages in one's repertoire facilitates the acquisition of additional languages (Cenoz & Valencia, 1994; Sagasta, 2003; Sanz, 2008; Arozena, 2017; Orcasitas-Vicandi, 2022).

To sum up, we can claim that significant differences are found between students' language contact and writing performance, supporting previous research on the impact of out of school language exposure to language learning (Llanes & Muñoz, 2013; Muñoz, 2014; Pujadas & Muñoz, 2020; Pattermore & Muñoz, 2020). Besides, the level of positive engagement in different activities outside the classroom plays a role in students' written performance. In this sense, results related to research question one revealed a statistical significant correlation between students' language contact through media and students' written performance. Our findings are also in line with previous investigations (Koolstra & Beentjes 1999; Bunting & Lindstrom, 2013; Khan *et al.*, 2014; Strobl & Baten, 2021; Ekpe *et al.*, 2021) reporting a positive correlation between out of school factors and language learning, and support the claim that the more use of out of school activities the more effective the leaning is. Besides, our findings are also in line with Strobl & Baten (2021), who suggested that staying abroad and using language with friends motivated students, and as a result, it had a positive impact on language use.

Moreover, interesting results were found by looking at participants' level of engagement during out of school activities. Results related to research question two indicated that, although the more contact with the target language outside school the better written scores obtained, there were differences in written scores regardless of the level of engagement in out-of-school activities. This is an area that requires further research.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study provides further support of the benefits of out of school language exposure for language learning. More specifically it shows the benefits of the use of media on students' English writing. In this study we have not only found a significant difference between students' language contact and writing performance, but the level of engagement in different out of school activities seem to play a role in students' written performance. Besides, our findings seem to suggest that the experience of staying abroad and using language with friends motivates students to use the language for real language use, and, as a result, it may have a positive impact on language use, in this particular case in English writing.

The present study also presents some limitations. First of all, the sample is too small to generalize the results. Secondly, no recording was possible during the semi-structured interviews, as students preferred not to be recorded during the interview. Thirdly, we have not considered hours of exposure to language and we have focused on the number and types of media. Further research might look at the impact of hours of exposure on students' writing performance, considering different levels of English proficiency and educational background.

In spite of these limitations, it is worth pointing out that our results suggest some pedagogical implications. First, since increased contact

with audio and visual materials, social media and social interaction seems to trigger interest for language use and learning, special attention is needed to encourage language learning beyond the classroom. We agree that a combination of exposure to language in the classroom and beyond is paramount when learning a language (Benson, 2013; Sundqvist & Sylvén, 2016; Olsson, 2016). In this sense, the use of media, together with a promotion of autonomous language learning may be a path to explore in teacher-training courses and in real language classrooms. Secondly, since individual attitudes towards languages in multilingual contexts may influence learners' engagement in out of school activities, the use of workshops to emphasize the benefits of multilingualism for third (English) language learning should also be encouraged. These may be addressed to teachers, parents and educational authorities.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1. Cuestionario:

Nos gustaría contar con tu ayuda para contestar estas preguntas. No es ninguna prueba y por lo tanto no hay respuestas 'correctas' o 'incorrectas', **ni siquiera tienes que escribir tu nombre**. Lo que nos interesa es tu verdadera opinión. Por favor, danos las respuestas de forma sincera, es la única manera de garantizar el éxito de la investigación. Muchas gracias por tu ayuda.

Primera parte: información general

- 1) Edad: ____
- 2) Sexo: Chico __ Chica __
- 3) ¿En qué curso de la EOI estás? ____
- 4) Lengua materna: Castellano __ Valenciano __ Ambas __ Otra (indica) _____
- 5) ¿Cuántos años llevas estudiando inglés? ____

6) ¿Estudias otro idioma aparte del Inglés? _____ ¿Cuál? _____

IMPORTANTE: Esta parte se trata del contacto **fuera del ámbito escolar**.

7) ¿En casa hablas en **valenciano** (sí / no), **castellano** (sí / no), **inglés** (sí / no)?

Indica las lenguas que utilizas para realizar las diferentes actividades:

Segunda parte: contacto lingüístico

En...	Valenciano	Castellano	Inglés	Otro
Veo películas (en versión original) Escucho música				
Escucho la radio				
Leo libros				
Veo la televisión				
Veo/Leo las noticias				
Busco información (Google, etc.)				
Utilizo redes sociales (Facebook, Whatsapp, Twitter, Instagram, etc.)				
Utilizo foros específicos				
Juego videojuegos				

APPENDIX 2. **WRITTEN EXPRESSION**

What are the advantages and disadvantages of Online Shopping? (**between 150- 200 words**)

¿Te gusta escribir **en inglés**?:

- a) Nada b) Muy poco c) Normal
- d) Bastante e) Mucho

¿Por qué? (Utiliza un mínimo de 20 palabras)